

CHILD'S RIGHT IN ISLAM: A PANACEA TO ENVIRONMENTAL DEGRADATION

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Abstract

Children of today, they say, are the leaders of tomorrow. For a nation to have a better tomorrow, the rights of its future leaders must be keenly administered. To achieve this, government and non-governmental organizations such as U. N. O., A. U. and UNICEF held meetings to fine-tune the rights of children. This was finally developed to what is known as Child's Right Act. Despite brainstorming during series of meetings held on the matter by these organizations, it was discovered that many salient rights of the children were not addressed in the Act. While some acts were not detailed, some have been abused by the parents which resulted to child immorality. Islam, on the other hand, has taken care of the rights of children from inception which has been embedded in the Glorious Qur'ān and traditions of Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W.). Adopting analytical method, this research work explains the Child's Right according to Islamic jurisprudence and highlights the omissions observed in the Child's Right Act. The paper affirms the divinity and infallibility of Islamic law and thereby recommend it.

Keywords: Child's Right, Environmental Degradation, Islamic Jurisprudence.

INTRODUCTION

Children's right was first given prominent recognition by the West at the United Nations' convention held on the 20th November, 1989.¹ This was followed by the World summit organized by the UNICEF for children from 29th to 30th September, 1990 at the United Nations Headquarters in New York. Thereafter, child's rights were proclaimed in Nigeria by the Organization of Africa Unity (O. A. U) now African Union (A. U) chapter in Abuja in 1991².

Islam, on the other hand, has been advocating for child's right since its inception. These are the rights granted the children by Allah, thus no individual or institution can overrule or obliterate it. The charter, proclamation or resolutions of the United Nations are, to say the least, not comparable to Allah's law stated in the Glorious Qur'ān. Some of the rights of a child as recognized in Islam are analyzed below:

1. **Right to Genetic Purity:** It is one of the rights of a child in Islam that his father marries a noble or decent woman; by this, he has chosen a good mother for him. Nobility or decency in this content does not necessarily mean beauty or wealth. What is essential in a woman are religion and character. Prophet Muhammad analyzes some of the prerequisites of marriage when he said a woman could be married because of her wealth, beauty, family and religion. Emphasis was later laid on a religious woman. It is generally assumed that a religious woman will be morally upright. The Glorious Qur'ān expatiates on the choice of a good spouse when Allah says:

And marry those among you who are single and the righteous among your servants. If they are poor, Allah will enrich them out of His grace, and surely, Allah is All-Embracing, All-Knowing. Qur'ān 24:32

Besides the religion, there are other things to be considered when choosing a spouse. In one of the traditions narrated by Ummul- Muminin, Aisha, (R. A.), Prophet Muhammad said:

“Be selective for your sperms and marry your equals”.³

Equality or compatibility in this ḥadith enjoins man to put many things into consideration when it comes to choosing a wife. For instance, a poor man marrying from a wealthy family may find it difficult to control both the wife and the children; likewise, a wealthy man who marries a local lady may not be satisfied with her ways of life. Same goes to educational and social aspect. Good character and moral conduct are other major factors to be considered in marriage. That was the reason the Prophet enjoins a would-be husband to study the family of his proposed wife when he says:

“Make choice for your sperms because women beget the likes of their brothers and sisters.”⁴

UthmanibnAbi-l-ĀsAthaqāfi, when advising his son on marriage said:

My son, a bridegroom is a farmer; let a man scrutinize where he shall plant his crop (because bad sweat at times procreate, therefore, make (right) choice even if it takes you a while.⁵

Genetic purity is one of the best ways to good and proper child upbringing in the contemporary age. Children usually inherit from their parents physical, mental and behavioural identities. This selection is not only peculiar to women, men are no saints; it is only that nature assigns more roles concerning child upbringing on women than men.

Despite the enormous importance of this right, it was omitted in the Child Right Act, 2003. The only Act found similar to it is Act 14⁶ (Right to Parental Care, Protection and Maintenance) which states as follows:

1. Every child has a right to parental care and protection and accordingly, no child shall be separated from his parents against the wish of the child except:
 - (a) For the purpose of his education and welfare; or
 - (b) In the exercise of a judicial determination in accordance with the provisions of this act, in the best interest of the child.
2. Every child has the right to maintenance by his parents or guardians in accordance with the extent of their means, and the child has the right, in appropriate circumstances, to enforce this right in the family court.

Right to Life: From the beginning of message of Prophet Muhammad, Islam has prohibited killing of children for any reason. Having children is a thing of joy which is marked with celebration, appreciation and giving *sadaqah* (charity). Prior to this period, the idea of killing children for frivolous reasons such as to protect their social standard, for fear of sustaining them and for gender disparity on the part of a girl child predominate the Society especially

among the Arabs. In the contemporary age of civilized world, abortion has become a common means of terminating children's life in many developed and developing countries. The situation is even worse nowadays that many countries are embracing same sex marriage knowing fully well that no procreation can occur through it.

Islam vehemently condemned this act with many verses of the Qur'an warning people against it and the expected consequences of the perpetrators.⁷

This right was also erroneously omitted in the Child Right Act. The two Acts whose contents are similar to it are Act 13⁸ with caption "Right to Health and Heal Service." which contains six (6) subsections and Act 17⁹ with caption "Right of the Unborn Child to Protection against Harm" under which appears the following:

1. A child may bring in action for damages against a person for harm or injury caused to the child willfully, recklessly, negligently, or through neglect before, during or after the birth of that child.
2. Where the father of an unborn child dies intestate, the unborn child is entitled, if he was conceived during the lifetime of his father, to be considered in the distribution of the estate of the deceased father.
3. Where the mother of an unborn child dies intestate before the child is delivered, the unborn child is entitled if he survives his mother, to be considered in the distribution of the estate of the deceased mother.

The content of the above Acts do not focus on the right of a child to life. Rather than enacting law that will mandate every citizen who has attain the age of marriage and has the resources to get married, the first law prepared the mind of the unborn child to sue his parents for damages while the remaining two centered on inheritance. Marriage is one of the criteria to measure the responsibility of a man.

Right to Breast-Feeding: Feeding the young ones with breast milk is a natural urge peculiar to all mammals, that is, both human beings and animals. Allah instructed mothers (human beings) to suckle their offspring with breast milk. This is the reason why it was created in them. Allah says

Mothers shall give suckle to their offspring for two whole year for those who desire to complete term.... Qur'an 2:233

Prophet Muhammad once enlightened women on the marvelous reward awaiting them for breastfeeding their children when he says: "And for the first sip of her milk which she give to her child, the mother gets the reward equivalent to giving life to a person."

Mother's milk gives babies natural health and energy. It is generally agreed by medical experts that breast milk is superior to artificial food used in feeding infants; it is seen as a well-balanced diet which enhance growth and also save them from many infectious diseases. It is encouraged to start breastfeeding a new born baby within thirty (30) minutes of birth. It is true that artificial milk extracted from animals accelerate physical growth of babies but children fed on breast

milk are known to be healthier, stronger, more intelligent and better adjusted psychologically.

In addition to afore-mentioned benefits of breast milk, it also contains colostrum which has Vitamin A in abundance; this is highly needed at the early days of a child as body resistance against external infection which many children are exposed to at their early stage of life. Medical experts of contemporary age have seen breast feeding as beneficial to both mother and child. As for the mother, exclusive breast feeding of her child for as long as possible reduces her risk of having breast and ovarian cancers. During this period, certain hormones, which reduce the risk of developing cancer are released. For the child, exclusive breast feeding reduces the risk of having heart disease and stroke at adult age.

Women nowadays are more concerned about wealth creation than family affairs, hence, most women cannot sacrifice the required time for breastfeeding due to their engagement in the labour force. Work should not impede a mother from playing her destined role of breastfeeding; crèche can be created in the workplace to allow easy and frequent breastfeeding of child by a nursing mother at work. There are some misconceptions about breast feeding which discourage women from it; this include the insinuation that infant formula is superior to mother's milk or that breast feeding deform the physical outlook of a woman. All these are wrong; rather, breast feeding makes children feel the soothing and invigorating warmth of their mother's lap while suckling the elixir of life from her breast. It creates a special closeness between mother and child.

As important as this right is to human existence, it was not included in the Child's Right Act. What could be considered close to it is Act 4 which states that "Every child has the right to survival and development"¹⁰

Right to Identity and Good Name

Islam considers the importance of the right to identity of human being. Nations, tribes or ethnic diversity does not undermine the personality of human being neither does it adds to its value. Having means of identification makes it easy for a community or nation to have accurate data of its citizens. Allah says:

O mankind! We created you from a single (pair) of male and female and made you into nations and tribes, that you know each other..

The first population census carried out in Nigeria was in 1963. With all the efforts put in place by the Federal Government since then till date, it has been difficult to get the accurate population of Nigerians. If the rules laid down in Islam pertaining to this act have been strictly followed, that is if registration of birth, death, as well as movement of people in and out of the country have been duly and consistently registered, perhaps it would have gone a long way in solving the problem of population census which would have only require daily update of existing data. The United Nations defines population census as "the total process of collecting, compiling and publishing demographic economic and social data pertaining to a specific time to all persons in a country or delimited part of a country"¹¹

Similarly, Islam emphasize on the right of a child to a good name after birth. This was contain in one of the prophetic traditions reported by Abu Daūd on the narration of Abu Dardā where Prophet Muhammad was reported to have said:

Surely, you shall be called upon on the Day of Resurrection by your name and that of your father, therefore, give yourselves good names.¹²

This hadith was replicated in Article 5 of the Child's Right Act 2003 which stated that "Every child has the right to a name and, accordingly, shall be given a name on his birth or such other date as is dictated by the culture of his parents or guardian."¹³

Names, as perceived by many people, reflect in the characters of the bearer. Parents should therefore be cognizant of the meaning of names they give to their children. It is permissible in Islam for a child to change his name after due consultation with Islamic Scholars if he grows up to discover that the name given to him by his parents is not meaningful. An example of this was seen when Prophet Muhammad changed names of some companions who consulted him for it.¹⁴

Right to Privacy: Advocating child's right to privacy in Islam is one of the ways to imbue moral value and ethics in the child's life. The etiquette of creating privacy for children who have come of age has been entrenched in many verses of the Glorious Qu'rān and *aḥādīth*. This will allow both the parents and children have time for themselves as well as do things according to their wishes with little or no interference. Allah says:

O you who believe! Let your slaves and slave-girls, and those among you who have not come of age of puberty ask your permission (before they come to your presence) on three occasions: before *FajrSalāt* (morning prayer), and while you put off your cloth for the noonday (rest), and after *Ishā' Salāt* (late-night prayer). (These) three times are of privacy for you; other than these times there is no sin on you or on them to move about, attending to each other. Thus Allah makes clear the *Ayāt* (the verses of the Qur'ān showing proofs for the legal aspects of permission for visits) to you. And Allah is All-Knowing, All-Wise. Qur'ān 24:58-59

Prophet Muhammad enjoins parents to make separate sleeping arrangements for their children as soon as they come of age. He says:

Instruct your children to observe (canonical) prayers when they are seven years old, punish them on it (if they don't comply) when they are ten years and let them sleep separately (male and female) from one another.¹⁵

It can be understood from the verses of the Glorious Qur'ān and hadith quoted above that only those children whose sense of perception are yet to develop should be allowed to enter their parents' room freely. As soon as they can be sensitive to the nude of a woman, they cannot enter their parents' room until they seek permission and are given. On the other hand, when a child cannot enter into his/her parents' room without been permitted, he/she is definitely entitled to a personal place where his/her own privacy is safe and whoever wants to enter must also seek permission especially if the child has attain maturity.

Article 8 Sub-section 1-3 of the child's right Act 2003 says:

1. Every child is entitled to his privacy, family life, home, correspondence, telephone conversation and telegraphic communications, except as provided in Sub-section (3).
2. No child shall be subjected to any interference with his right in Sub-section (1) of this section, except as provided in Sub-section (3).
3. Nothing in the provision of Sub-section (1) & (2) of this section shall affect the rights of parents and, where applicable, legal guardians, to exercise reasonable supervision and control over the conduct of their children and wards.¹⁶

Privacy of a child should not be misconstrued to absolute freedom of the child from the control of the parents. This should not give room to negligence or over-pampering of the child as it may lead to another serious havoc in the society. Sub-section (3) of the Article which was referred to in the two preceding sections emphasize the need of parents in supervising and mentoring the affairs of their children. Imam A-Baqir, one of the leaders of Ahlul-Bayt, says:

The worst among parents is he whose kindness (to his children) drags him to over-pampering.¹⁷

Right to Education: Education means a process of leading or bringing up, of nurturing, rearing, molding or shaping (a child) into a type of visible standard of behavior. Islam attaches great importance to the education of children. It is one of the fundamental obligations of parents to give proper education to their children. Through this, children shall have a solid foundation on which they can build their desired goal in life. Parents are therefore made directly responsible for teaching their children how to read and write. This is clearly illustrated in some of the teachings of Prophet Muhammad. He once said:

A father cannot give any creed to his son better than to imbue him knowledge that will benefit him or shield him from ignorance.¹⁸ It is important to start educating children right from their tender age when their brain is still sharp and their mind free from ephemeral thoughts. In Article 15 of the Act, it was emphasize that children must undergo free, compulsory and universal basic education which shall be provided by the government of Nigeria while the children's parents/guardians shall be responsible for their secondary education. The Act even went to the extent of recommending fine or/and imprisonment for parents who fail in this capacity.¹⁹

Before Chief Obafemi Awolowo led Action Group government introduced free and compulsory primary education in Western Region in January 17, 1955, many parents could not afford sending their children to school; many parents could not even define its importance. But the situation changed with the introduction of Universal Primary Education (U. P. E) for the Western Region in 1955.²⁰ It is established that Islam emphasizes on education of children but for education to be free depends on the financial capacity of the nation. It is not mandatory under Islamic law and ethics that government of a particular state or nation should shoulder all the financial burden of education of her subjects; therefore, if the Government can finance Primary education, parents also should be able to take over from there. It is stated in the Glorious Qur'an that the father should be responsible for the expenses of up-bringing his children. Allah says:

...but the father of the child shall bear the cost of mother's food and clothing on a reasonable basis. No person shall have a burden laid on him greater than he can bear. No mother shall be treated unfairly on account of her child, no father on account of his child. And on the (father's) heir is incumbent the like of that (which was incumbent on the father)... Qur'an 2: 233

Right to Equal Treatment: Children in Islam are entitled to equitable treatment regardless of sex or age. One of the habits of the people of *Jahiliyyah* period (period of ignorance: this refers to the period that precedes the prophet hood of Muhammad SAW) was infanticide. The then Arabs were fond of eliminating their female children with the notion that they are weaker sex. Islam eradicate it and some other *Jahiliyyah* vices. Islam does not discriminate in the process of observing religious rights as well as awarding rewards and punishments.²¹ The conditional relief granted to women on certain religious obligations is not meant to undervalue them as female but to allow them attend to the call of nature. Gender discrimination is not limited to a particular sex. The most common is the love of many parents to have a male child. This has been in existence from time immemorial as it reflects in the quest of the mother of Maryam when she prayed to Allah to make her conceive a male child²² In the past, preference used to be given to a male child in Yoruba land over his female counterpart simply because he shall grow up to become the heir apparent who maintains the family name as long as he lives.

Sometimes, parents show unguided love for one of their children over others; Islam also guide against such act to avoid creating enmity among them. A typical example is what was narrated by Nu'mān ibn Bashīr My father gave me a gift, 'Amrah bint Rawāhah said I should not accept it until the Prophet was briefed about it. My father got to the Prophet and said; I gave my son a gift from 'Amrah bint Rawāhah, she instructed me to inform you O Messenger of Allah! The Prophet asked: did you give your remaining sons a similar gift? He said no. the Prophet said: Fear Allah and be just among your children. He returned and withdrawn the gift.²³

In a related hadith, the Prophet admonished parents on equal treatments among children when he said: "Be just among your children in creed (distribution) as you love Allah to be just among you in righteousness and mercy".²⁴ Islam has bridged the gap of discrimination of any kind. This is stated in the farewell sermon of Prophet Muhammad where he said among other things:

All mankind is from Adam and Eve, an Arab has no superiority over a non-Arab nor a non-Arab over an Arab; also a white has no superiority over a black nor does a black have any superiority over a white except by piety and good intention.²⁵

This is also clearly demonstrated during hajj exercise where Presidents of Countries or eminent personalities from various parts of the world receive equal treatment, not minding their status, colour or sex.

Article 10 of the stated that:

A Child shall not be subjected to any form of discrimination merely by reason of belonging to a particular community or ethnic group or by reason of his/her place of birth, origin, sex, religion or political opinion.²⁶

Observations

Most of the rights of the Child, as stated above, when closely examined, have either been violated or mismanaged. On genetic purity, many parents in the contemporary society have failed in their parental role simply because the foundation of their marriage was laid on deception and falsehood. Morality which is the core value of good parenting cannot be found in many contemporary families and since this supposed to be the bedrock of a decent society, its failure has contributed to moral decadence in the Society.

Right to life and breastfeeding has also been bastardized. In the contemporary age of civilized world, abortion has become a common means of terminating children's life in many developed and developing countries. The situation is even worse nowadays that many countries are embracing same sex marriage and is illegally practiced in many Countries knowing fully well that no procreation can occur through it.

Recently in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria, about forty (40) young men were apprehended by Security operatives when they preparing to marry one another. On breastfeeding, women nowadays are more concerned about wealth creation than family affairs; hence, most women cannot sacrifice the required time for breastfeeding due to their engagement in the labour force.

Similarly, right to education of children is not seriously monitored especially in our contemporary Nigeria. The number of Out-of-School children in the Country increases on daily basis due to various reasons ranging from inadequate infrastructural facilities to lack of enough qualified teachers, insecurity, low household income etc.

There are Schools across the country where structures built in early 50s when Chief ObafemiAwolowo introduced free primary education in the Southwest are used as classroom despite their deplorable conditions. Some pupils have no locker or chair; no conducive learning environment, to say the least. Likewise, despite the fact that teachers in public schools retire from service every time, government find it difficult to recruit new ones.

Security failure of the country has also worsened the children's enrolment in schools. Children are being kidnapped in their schools by bandits without exception from Primary School to the University. This has discouraged many willing pupils/students as well as many parents from further attempts.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The above observations on Child's Right Acts have shown clearly that the Acts suffered implementation in many ways and of various circumstances. It is on this note that the following measures are recommended.

1. The foundation of a peaceful society starts from a good family. Genetic purity should therefore be given optimum priority. Men and women of virtue are recommended for one another in the Glorious Qur'ān.²⁷ A bad tree rarely produce good fruit. Parents should endeavor to train their children to become role models in the society.

2. Allah (SWT) is the Creator and Sustainer. Population control should be annexed through cancelling of couples and not through forbidden acts like same sex marriage or abortion. The right of children to life must be respected.

3. Right of Child to education is relatively maintained in Southwestern part of Nigeria.

Virtually all the 943 public primary schools in Ekiti State have been renovated by the State government. Likewise, the State secondary schools through a World Bank assisted project tagged “Adolescent Girls Initiative for Learning and Empowerment” (AGILE).

Thanks Ekiti State Government for recruiting over 3000 teachers to fill some of the vacuums in the State Primary and Secondary Schools between 2019 and 2023. Government at various levels in other parts of the Country should wake up to their responsibilities by providing human and material resources needed to increase enrolment of school age children at various levels.

Most importantly, religious education should be given optimum priority because it is through this that children could be trained the act of piety. It is said that fear of God is the beginning of wisdom.

4. Breastfeeding should be made compulsory for nursing mothers. It is an instruction from Allah. Women should be enlightened more on the benefits of breast milk to their babies; government may also introduce something like incitement for mothers whose babies show great sign of exclusive breastfeeding. In February 2020, Ekiti State government approved six months maternity leave for female workers in the State public service to allow exclusive breastfeeding.²⁸

5. It is true that Islam support child privacy, this does not mean that parents should off their hands from the affairs of their children; they need constant admonition and guidance. One of the key parental role is to give moral upbringing to the children and this could be done perfectly through having close contact or constant interaction with them. By doing this, parents are playing the Shepard’s according to the hadith of Prophet Muhammad which says:

You are all Shepard and shall all be asked about his flocks of Sheep. The Emperor is a Shepard. A man is a Shepard over his household. A woman is a Shepard over her husband’s home and his children.²⁹

CONCLUSION

This paper has attempted to analyze the conformity of the Child Right Act 2003 of the Federal Republic of Nigeria with the Divine rights of Children as applicable in Islamic jurisprudence. Among the rights of children, those ones that were mentioned in the Act were linked up with either the Qur’ānic verses or hadith of Prophet Muhammad and others that were not mentioned were enlisted as appeared in the *Shari’ah*. The purpose of this Act is to give the children their required recognition as human being as well as to lay good foundation for their future endeavors. Child’s right, as presented in Islamic jurisprudence was seen as the best protector of child’s welfares rightly from before his birth till he attains adulthood.

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